

***N*-Bromosuccinimide as an interfacial alleviator for Br/I exchange in perovskite for solar cell fabrication**

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Abstract

Engineering the surface at the rear interface between the perovskite and the hole transporting material is of paramount importance to minimize non-radiative losses. We report the use of *N*-bromosuccinimide (*NBS*), as an interfacial alleviator to influence crystallization of the perovskite and defect passivation. The *NBS* treatment promotes added charge extraction and yields devices with improved photovoltaic performance. Thus formed perovskite layers exhibit grain size increment and lowered trap density. An improved device performance was noted with an optimized concentration of 0.5% *NBS* as compared to pristine perovskite due to the open circuit voltage and short circuit current density enhancement. The coordination of bromide influences the crystal lattice as shown by polarization modulated-infrared reflection-absorption spectroscopy, which in turn may influence charge transport and interfacial properties.

Keywords: *N*-Bromo succinimide, grain size, open circuit voltage, PMIRRAS, density of states

INTRODUCTION

Organic-inorganic hybrid perovskites are the subject of intense investigations for the fabrication of solar cells. Owing to their high absorption coefficient, tunable band gap and unparalleled semiconducting properties, promising results for photovoltaics (PV) and optoelectronics applications have been documented.¹ The reported power conversion efficiency (PCE) in perovskite solar cells (PSCs) has shown exceptional boost from a mere 3.8% to 25.5%²⁻³, and are adaptable to solution-processable manufacturing routes.⁴⁻⁶ The use of perovskite as a light harvester impose challenges in terms of the number of defects at the grain boundaries that stem from its polycrystalline nature. Defect density is considerably higher as compared to monocrystalline materials.⁷⁻¹⁰ The free charge carrier diffusion is hindered by trap states resulting from grain boundaries or defects that leads to non-radiative recombination, thereby reducing charge carrier lifetime.¹¹⁻¹⁵ Arguably, these polycrystalline grain boundaries increase the density of trap states and influence opto-electrical merit, leading to an increase in charge recombination rates.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Annealing at high temperature may leads to the slow decomposition of the organic cation and formation of vacancies. Halide ions may fill the site of the vacant inorganic cation which enhances crystal degradation at the grain boundaries and defects also increases moisture permeability.²⁰⁻²² To improve device performance, it is of paramount importance to optimize the surface for defect passivation, reduction in charge recombination, trap states and grain size increment.²³⁻²⁴ Passivating agents have been reported to reduce non-radiative decay, improve moisture tolerance, increase open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor (FF).²⁵⁻²⁶ Organic molecules having Lewis acid or base properties or polymers that form hydrogen bonds with the perovskite surface reduce trap states and increment in grain size.²⁷⁻³⁴ In this context passivating or doping of the perovskite with bromide or chloride in lieu of iodide ions has also been suggested to can be beneficial for PSCs.³⁵

The stability of PSCs under moisture and elevated temperatures is a considerable challenge.³⁶⁻
³⁸ The intrinsic degradation of the perovskite induces the segregation or precipitation of PbI_2 and the disappearance of methylammonium iodide (MAI) or formamidinium iodide (FAI) upon exposure to moisture or elevated temperatures.²² Through the use of hydrophobic materials, prolonged device stability was investigated using polarization modulated-infrared reflection-absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS).³⁹ In some cases, the I^- or Br^- ions migrate out of the perovskite lattice, creating large defects that elevate charge recombination at the grain boundaries and at the perovskite/HTM interface.⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴ To address such instability issues, various layered (2D) and bilayer of layered and 3-dimensional (3D) was reported.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹ One such strategy is the use of ammonium halide-based materials that block migration of the ionic elements from the surface of the perovskite.^{50,51} Additionally, the use of bromide in the perovskites can allow structural transition from the metastable tetragonal phase to the more stable cubic phase. The selection of such materials should take into account (i) energetically alignment with the band gap of the perovskite to minimize losses, (ii) consistent charge carrier mobility, and (iii) enhance exciton binding energy. Modified interfaces not only limit the moisture attack, but also improve device performance by decreasing surface recombination and interfacial contacts.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ In most cases, the passivating agents employed to mitigate defects are poorly conductive and occasionally form aggregates at the charge selective interfaces which may impede the extraction of photogenerated charge carriers.⁵⁵

We demonstrate that *N*-haloimides such as *N*-bromo succinimide (*NBS*) are a source of bromide ions and can be used as an alleviator atop of the mixed perovskite $(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}$ to improve the crystal quality, defects reduction, and performance enhancement. We employed *NBS* as an interfacial layer in the device architecture FTO/bl- TiO_2 /meso- TiO_2 / $(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}$ /*NBS*/Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag. *NBS* use shown improvement in stability and charge transport properties by reducing the carrier recombination

rates, V_{oc} improvement at an optimized concentration that is attributed to Br^-/I^- exchange in the perovskite layer. The *NBS* treatment led to an increase in the built-in potential and yielded higher V_{oc} . The device performance and the grain size increase through Oswald ripening, an increase PCE (18.12%) with a V_{oc} of 1130 mV, short circuit current (J_{sc}) 22.18 mA/cm², FF of 71.9% was measured. *NBS* is common chemical reagent, readily used as a source of bromine and routinely employed in organic chemistry for various substitution or brominating reactions.⁵⁶ *NBS* was reported as a bromide precursor for stable and highly luminescent perovskite nanocrystals.⁵⁷ Our results suggests that *NBS* is potentially active for halide exchange, grain growth and device stability. The *NBS* treatment and its role was probed using an array of spectroscopic techniques, including PM-IRRAS measurements.

Figure 1. Mixed perovskite (MAPbBr₃)_{0.15}(FAPbI₃)_{0.85} with *NBS* treatment (A) device architecture of the perovskite used (B) schematic illustration of pristine PSK and reaction of *NBS* with isopropanol during the post-annealing treatment at 100°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The device architecture and possible reaction between the *NBS* and perovskite are depicted in Figure 1. Different concentrations of *NBS* in isopropanol (IPA) (3 mg/mL, 5 mg/mL and 10

mg/mL) was investigated for treatment of the perovskite layer. For the ease of terminology, they are defined as 0.3%, 0.5%, 1% *NBS* and mixed perovskite as pristine PSK respectively. Post-deposition treatment using *NBS* to pristine PSK promotes recrystallization of the perovskite layer into larger grains. We speculate that the Oswald ripening process helps in refining the small crystals into the larger grains post annealing and allows I^- / Br^- anion exchange up to a certain concentration.⁵⁸⁻⁵⁹ We noted up to 0.5% *NBS*, the crystallinity of the perovskite significantly improved and this has bearing on device performance, on further increasing the concentration (1% *NBS*), large grain sizes can be achieved but at the cost of device performance. PM-IRRAS experiments suggest release of bromide anions by *NBS* treatments and the latter can be formed thermally during the deposition process through oxidation of the solvent (isopropyl alcohol) by *NBS* (*Scheme S2*). *NBS* oxidation of secondary alcohols is expected to release HBr .⁶⁰⁻⁶¹ The increased proportion of bromide in the material was evidenced spectroscopically. The inclusion of bromide ion from *NBS* and halide exchange can act as a driving force for efficient charge carrier extraction can also contribute to the device's stability.⁶² Furthermore, improved-quality perovskite microstructure are formed by virtue of rate constant decrement, which favors large crystal and homogenous layer formation.⁶³ Arguably, this stems from lower activation energy for grain boundary mobility that promote grain growth and leads to enlarged grains in the perovskite layer.⁶² (*Scheme S1*).

Figure 2: Structural, diffraction, absorption and emission spectroscopy of the pristine PSK and *NBS/PSK* layers at varying concentration, (A) UV-Visible absorption, (B) Photoluminescence spectra, (C) X-ray diffraction patterns of the pristine PSK and with 0.3%, 0.5% and 1% *NBS/PSK* and (D) Magnified area of the diffractograms in the low 2θ range (12° - 15°).

It can be deduced from spectra (Figure 2A) that the absorbance properties of the *NBS* treated perovskite layer remain unaltered up to a certain concentration (0.3% and 0.5% *NBS*), with an excitonic peak at 750 nm. However, we note higher absorption with 0.3% and 0.5% *NBS* treatment compared to that of the pristine PSK. This we assigned to improved crystallinity. With an increase in concentration (1% *NBS*), the intensity for the excitonic peak at 750 nm decreases, and is in accordance with diffractograms, which illustrates a higher amount of PbI_2 for 1% *NBS*.

To substantiate the influence of *NBS* on the electro-optical properties, we performed steady state PL measurements on quartz substrates using 450-nm excitation (Figure 2B). The emission spectra exhibit PL maxima centered at 762nm, 764nm, 766nm and 770 nm for pristine and 0.3%, 0.5% and 1% treated *NBS*, respectively. A passivated perovskites shows gradual reduction in the PL intensity for 0.3% and 0.5% *NBS*, attributed to the passivated trap states on

the surface or to the grain boundaries.⁶⁴ With the increase in *NBS* concentration (1%), the PL curves shift slightly to longer wavelengths and attains maximum PL intensity similar to that of pristine PSK. The PL emission results (0.5% *NBS*) reflects the device PV performance and diffractograms.

We recorded the diffraction patterns in a thin film geometry (Figure 2C and 2D) and the diffractograms (Figure 2C), suggest similarity upon *NBS* treatment. The peak at 12.92° represents the (001) PbI₂ while 14.34° represents the characteristic peak (110) of the perovskite. On increasing the concentration up to 0.5% *NBS*, the intensity of the perovskite peak (110) increases, attributed to the higher crystallinity. In case of 1% *NBS* the intensity of the PbI₂ (001) peak gradually increases, as compared to the pristine PSK, 0.3% and 0.5% *NBS* treated PSK. Higher *NBS* treatment can induce lattice strain to the perovskite crystal that can promote the formation of precursor materials. From the diffractograms (Figure 2D), a monotonic shift of the peak <110> towards the lower 2θ values can be deduced. Arguably, we ascribed this peak shifting to the change in chemical environment or the strain suffered by the perovskite lattice at higher concentrations of *NBS* treatment.

The *NBS* treatment induces modifications in the crystallinity of the material which are evidenced by the changes in the vibrational spectra, grain size and ultimately, in the electronic characteristics and overall performance of the devices. We follow the change in the vibrational signature of the material upon *NBS* treatment through PM-IRRAS spectroscopy. PM-IRRAS has been previously shown to be well adapted to collecting the vibrational spectrum of hybrid perovskite materials and possess sufficient sensitivity to detect the presence of even single molecular layers.^{39, 65} The samples deposited by spin coating the precursor solution onto gold-coated glass substrates for PM-IRRAS. The PM-IRRAS spectrum of the pristine PSK is shown in (Figure 3A) along with the assignment of the most important bands.⁶⁶⁻⁶⁷ The *NBS* treatment results in significant changes in the spectrum, even for the low *NBS* concentrations, 0.02% and

0.2% *NBS* samples {(Figure 3B), black and orange curves, respectively}. Notably, regardless of the concentration of the *NBS* used (0.02 – 1%), no signals corresponding to the presence of *NBS* appeared. Indeed, the most significant IR absorption bands of *NBS* (shown in Figure 3B for clarity), are absent in the differential PM-IRRAS spectra of the *NBS*-treated perovskite. Instead, we observed an enhancement in the formamidinium (FA) bands that is indicative of an overall modification of the material's crystallinity.

Figure 3. Differential PM-IRRAS spectra of (A) the pristine PSK before *NBS* treatment (B) and differential PM-IRRAS spectra following treatment with 0.02 (black spectrum) and 0.2% (orange spectrum) *NBS*. The ATR spectrum of *NBS* is shown in green for comparison, along with the reference spectra of MAPbBr₃ (red spectrum) and MAPbI₃ (blue spectrum).

The absence of clear signals attributable to the presence of *NBS* on the material's surface evidences that it underwent a chemical transformation during the deposition or subsequent annealing step. Signals ascribed to the possible by-products, such as succinimide or *N*-hydroxysuccinimide are also absent. Instead, we observe a decrease in the $\delta_s(\text{NH}_3^+)$ signal assigned to perovskite containing methyl ammonium (MA) iodide, and an increase of the $\delta_s(\text{NH}_3^+)$ signal assigned to perovskite containing MA bromide. The two signals are close in energy (1470 and 1458 cm^{-1} , respectively), but clearly distinguishable when compared to the

pristine PSK. Based on these observations, we conclude that the deposition of *NBS* results in the incorporation of additional bromide ions into the material. In the case of the 0.2 and 1% samples, the increase in intensity of the FA bands is significant (+15% and +82%, respectively) and suggests a more substantial modification of the material's crystallinity or, to a change in the polarizability of the material. Furthermore, we note that the 1% (highest concentration) treated *NBS* sample also evidences a slow chemical alteration leading to the appearance of bromomethane (CH_3Br) signals (antisymmetric stretching vibration at 2964 cm^{-1} and symmetric bending vibration at 1264 cm^{-1}) over the course of several days (Figure S1). These signals are accompanied by the associated grow-in of signals which can be attributed to ammonia at ca. 1100 cm^{-1} , thereby indicating that the excess bromide ions introduced by the *NBS* treatment may be involved in an SN_2 reaction with the MA^+ cations of the material to form CH_3Br and NH_3 .

We probed the role of *NBS* by means of XPS measurements (Figure 4) and the narrow scan survey is presented in Figure 4A. The comparison of the core level peaks of C and Br attributing the surface elemental properties of the pristine PSK as well as the *NBS* treated ones are shown (Figure 4B-4F). The C1s spectra were compared and the peak at the lower binding energy (284.6 eV) (Figure 4B-4E) is related to C-C and C-H bonds. The C-N peak of FA and MA components have their binding energy at around 286.4 eV .⁶⁸ The peak at higher binding energy 288.3 eV is related to $\text{C}=\text{NH}_2^+$ of the organic cations. On treatment with *NBS*, the enhancement of the peak area at 288.3 eV at higher concentration signals overall chemical transformation or the crystallinity achieved due to the annealing step after *NBS* deposition. We also note an increase in the area of corresponding C1s peak with the higher concentration of *NBS* treatment (Table S2). In the Br 3d spectra (Figure 4F), the binding energies of Br 3d3 and Br 3d5 peaks are 69.4 eV and 68.4 eV , respectively.⁶⁹ The increase in intensity of the Br 3d peak, suggests the role of *NBS* and in *NBS* treated PSK, a shift of 0.4 eV (Br 3d) occurs with respect to pristine

PSK, attributed to the exchange of bromide with the iodide ions. In the Pb 4f spectra (Figure 5A), 0.5% *NBS* shows peak shifting to higher binding energy with 0.2 eV as compared to pristine PSK.⁶⁹ This we ascribed to the formation of PbX_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Br}^-$, I^-)⁷⁰ as a result of exchange of some of the I^- by the excess Br^- ions from the *NBS*, no noticeable shift was noted for 0.3% *NBS* treatment. For 1% *NBS*, we observe the Pb 4f peak shifts towards lower binding energy (Figure S2-S3), due to appropriate coordination between lead cations and halides.⁷¹ The evolution of N 1s peak (Figure 5B), shows a shift of 0.34 eV for the 0.5% *NBS* compared to pristine PSK (Figure S5-S7). The I 3d-peaks (Figure S4) of 0.5% and 1% *NBS* shifted to higher binding energy, while for the pristine PSK and 0.3% treated *NBS* it remains unaltered.

The microstructure was examined using scanning electron microscopy (Figure S8) and we note (Figure S8C-D) enlargement in the grain size of crystals on *NBS* treatment. We noted the grain size to be ~274 nm for pristine, while for the 0.3%, 0.5% and 1% *NBS* treated perovskite 355, 596 and 841 nm respectively. The 1% *NBS* treatment shows grains enlarged to a large extent.⁷²

Figure 4: X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (A) survey spectra of the pristine PSK and with *NBS* treatment, (B-E) high resolution deconvoluted spectra of C1s peak of various layers and (F) bromine Br 3d peaks spectra for different samples.

Figure 5: XPS survey spectra of the pristine PSK and 0.5% *NBS* treated PSK (A) Pb 4f peak (B) N 1s peak.

Figure 6: (A) Cross sectional SEM-image of the fabricated device with 0.5% *NBS*/PSK; and contact angle measurements for (B) the pristine PSK, (C) 0.3% *NBS*/PSK (D) 0.5% *NBS*/PSK and (E) 1% *NBS*/PSK.

The typical cross-sectional SEM image of the devices fabricated using 0.5% *NBS* (Figure 6A), illustrates the thickness of the blocking and mesoporous TiO₂ to 131 nm, the PSK c.a. 670 nm, while the hole transport layer (Spiro-OMeTAD) was 152 nm. From the vertical capping of the layers, we noted limited grain boundaries with large crystal size. Goniometry measurements (Figure 6B-E) of the contact angle values for the pristine PSK (average angle = $77\pm 1^\circ$) and different concentrations of *NBS* (average angles, 0.3% = $86\pm 1^\circ$, 0.5% = $94\pm 1^\circ$, 1% = $95\pm 1^\circ$) increases respectively, evidencing the role of *NBS* in modifying the surface properties and induced hydrophobicity.

The *J-V* curves of fabricated PSCs with pristine or *NBS* treated perovskites are shown (Figure 7A) and results are summarized in Table 1. Pristine PSK gave a PCE of 16.69% ($V_{oc} = 1050$ mV, $J_{sc} = 21.15$ mA/cm², FF = 74.69%), while device fabricated with 0.5% *NBS* outperformed and yielded a PCE of 18.12% (Figure 7C). With the increase in *NBS* concentration up to 0.5% we note an increment in V_{oc} by 80 mV, ascribed to a reduction in defect-induced recombination. For 0.3% and 0.5% *NBS* based devices a V_{oc} of 1130 mV was measured, with minute decrement in FF. Our results shows an increase in PCE by 8.6% with respect to control devices and the process can be adopted for fabrication of high-performance devices. For 1% *NBS*, the device

performance is reduced. The enhancement with 0.5% *NBS* is attributed to the increased V_{oc} and reduced recombination of photo-generated charges at the interface of the perovskite layer, which is reflected also by the large value of the shunt resistance ($90.19 \text{ k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$). Statistical data (Figure S9) derived from ten individual devices suggest adequate reproducibility. The external quantum efficiencies (EQE) of the PSCs shows (Figure 7B) increment with 0.5% *NBS* treatment. The improved light harvesting and charge extraction are attributed to the increased absorbance and reduced emission intensity of *NBS* treated PSK (Figure 2A and 2B). The trend in J - V curve and EQE are in accordance with the optical and XRD measurements.

Figure 7: (A) Current-voltage characteristics of PSCs with and without *NBS* treatment under Air-Mass (AM) 1.5G illumination, (B) corresponding EQE, (C) comparative J - V curves of the pristine PSK and with 0.5% *NBS*/PSK, and (D) maximum power point tracking for the pristine PSK and 0.5% *NBS*/PSK devices without encapsulation for 92 h under 1 sun illumination at ambient condition.

To correlate the PV performances with the device stability, we performed maximum power point tracking (MPPT) measurements for the pristine and 0.5% *NBS* treated PSCs (Figure 7D). The improved power output was observed for 0.5% *NBS* treated PSCs and to test their long-term stability, un-encapsulated devices were kept under continuous illumination at 1 sun at room temperature with a relative humidity of 50-60%. The pristine PSK device lost its initial J_{sc} value and retained only around 10% after 20 h of continuous illumination, while the 0.5% *NBS* treated devices showed an initial drop followed by a much slower decline in the photocurrent value. Shelf life of the pristine PSK and *NBS* treated devices was examined by storing the un-encapsulated PSCs in a box under relative humidity of 40-50% (Figure S10). The PSCs showed an improved trend in stability up to 8 days (Figure S10A). However, at higher *NBS* concentration the stability decreases gradually after 70 days of storage (Figure S10B).

Table 1. PSCs photovoltaics parameters for pristine and *NBS* treated perovskites.

Sample	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_s (Ω .cm ²)	R_{sh} (k Ω .cm ²)
PSK	1056	21.15	74.69	16.69	4.24	4.47
0.3% <i>NBS</i> /PSK	1132	21.33	71.99	17.39	4.63	40.97
0.5% <i>NBS</i> /PSK	1136	22.18	71.90	18.12	4.19	90.19
1% <i>NBS</i> /PSK	1104	21.02	71.76	16.65	4.97	7.87

To unravel the role of *NBS* on the defect state and high value of shunt resistance achieved, thermal admittance spectroscopy (TAS) was performed (Figure 8A–8C).⁷³⁻⁷⁴ We measured the capacitance-frequency ($C-f$) curve at room temperature (Figure 8A) and variable temperature (Figures S11A and 11B), identical behaviors of the capacitance was noted. The plateau in the intermediate frequency (IF) range corresponds to the dielectric relaxation in the perovskites

that can be described by the geometrical capacitance per unit area $C_g = \epsilon\epsilon_0/L$ (ϵ and ϵ_0 refer to the dielectric constant and the permittivity of the vacuum, respectively, L is the layer thickness). The geometrical capacitance is temperature independent. However, the capacitance behavior in the low frequency (LF) range shows dependency on temperature and ascribed to the interfacial properties of the device. The capacitance in the LF range increases with the increase in temperature, however due to lower charge extraction and transportation, capacitance build-up at the perovskite/HTL interface can also occur. The capacitance build-up is lower for *NBS* treated devices, suggesting improved charge extraction.

Figure 8: Thermal admittance spectroscopy of pristine PSK and *NBS* treated devices, (A) Capacitance as a function of frequency at room temperature (298.15 K) for the pristine PSK and with 0.5% *NBS*, (B) plots showing the $f \times dC/df$ versus frequency at room temperature (C) Mott-Schottky plot for the pristine PSK and with 0.5% *NBS/PSK* and (D) trap density of states (N_T) of the devices at 298.15 K.

The trap density (N_T) for the device was calculated using the following equations:

$$N_T(E_\omega) = \frac{V_{bi}}{qWk_B T} \left(-f \frac{dC}{df} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$E_\omega = k_B T \ln \left(\frac{v_0}{f} \right) \quad (2)$$

where E_ω is the demarcation energy and f is the applied angular frequency. The attempt-to-escape frequency (ATEF, v_0) was derived from $(-f \frac{dC}{df})$ vs. frequency profile (Figure 8B), as reported elsewhere.^{25,32} We calculated the build-in potential (V_{bi}) and depletion layer width (W) from C^{-2} - V plots by performing Mott Schottky analysis (Supporting info.). An improved build-in potential, of 1050 mV for the 0.5 % *NBS* treated was extracted at 10 kHz, while pristine PSK based PSC gave a value of 990 mV (Figure 8C), this increment is in accordance to the J - V curves. In a similar fashion, with the increase in the build-in potential (V_{bi}), the depletion width increases from 44 nm to 52 nm for the 0.5% *NBS* treated PSC. The 0.5% *NBS* treated PSC (Figure 8D) showed lower trap densities ($1.384 \times 10^{18} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) compared to pristine PSK ($1.724 \times 10^{18} \text{ eV}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) PSC, implying that *NBS* treatment reduces the overall trap states located above the valence band of the perovskite and thus improves the V_{oc} .

The defect energy distribution shows a broad band with a maximum peak at $E_\omega = 0.181 \text{ eV}$ for pristine PSK based PSCs which shifts to lower energy (0.1799 eV) for 0.5% *NBS* treated PSCs. We ascribe this to the presence of shallow traps, and it is similar to the value of FAPbI_3 perovskites.³³ Additionally, typical density of deep traps ($>0.25 \text{ eV}$) was also observed in lower frequency regions that shows reduction in *NBS* treated PSCs. These deep defects could be related to the origin of hysteresis and originated due to the polarization of the materials at the interface.³⁴

CONCLUSION

To summarize, we report the use of *N*-bromo succinimide (*NBS*) as an interfacial alleviator on the perovskite layer. The employment of *NBS* reduces bulk and interfacial defects by refilling the grain boundaries and augmenting the crystal growth, beneficial for device application. In

contrast to molecular modulators currently used to mitigate such defects form poorly conductive aggregates at the perovskite interface with the charge collection layer, impeding the extraction of photogenerated charge carriers. PM-IRRAS spectroscopy shows that *NBS* does not stay on the surface of the perovskite. Instead, it undergoes a chemical reaction during the deposition process that results in the presence of bromide anions. Admittance and PL spectroscopy measurements support lower trap density and increase charge extraction. An optimal value of 0.5% *NBS* treatment showed an increment in the efficiency value from 16.69% to 18.12% due to the reduction in charge recombination that improves the V_{oc} . This reduced charge recombination was attributed to lower trap density near to the valence band of the perovskite, and gave high value of shunt resistance. Improved moisture and photo stability for 0.5% *NBS* treated devices as compared to the pristine perovskite was noted, suggesting use of *N*-haloimides for device performance enhancement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Device Fabrication

The fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glasses (TEC15) was used as electrode and were cleaned prior to use, firstly by ultrasonication (2% Hellmanex water solution for 30 minutes) followed by rinsing with deionized water, acetone and isopropanol (IPA) sequentially and finally the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 30 minutes for the removal for further residue. TiO₂ compact layer was deposited on the cleaned FTO substrate via spray pyrolysis at 500 °C using a precursor solution of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) in anhydrous ethanol (1:19). After the spraying, the substrates were left at 500 °C for 30 minutes and left to cool down to acquire room temperature. Followed by this, a 150–200 nm of mesoporous TiO₂ layer was deposited by spin coating process, for this a (1:8) TiO₂ paste (Dyesol 30 NR-D) diluted in ethanol for 30 s at 4000 rpm was used. The substrates were dried at 125 °C and then annealed until 500 °C in a four-step temperature ramp and maintained at 500°C for 30 min to

allow transformation of amorphous TiO₂ into anatase phase. When room temperature is attained, the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 15 minutes and transferred to an argon-filled glove-box for perovskite layer deposition. The precursor solution for preparing the mixed perovskite (MAPbBr₃)_{0.15}(FAPbI₃)_{0.85} was prepared by dissolving FAI (1 M), PbI₂ (1.2 M), MABr (0.2 M), and PbBr₂ (0.2 M) in anhydrous DMF: DMSO 4:1 (v:v). The perovskite solution was spin coated in a two-step sequence at 1000 and 6000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second step, 110 μL of chlorobenzene was dripped as an antisolvent approach on the substrate 5s prior the end of the spinning process. The perovskite coated substrates were annealed at 100 °C for 1 h in a glovebox. On acquiring room temperature, the passivation layer (0.3%, 0.5% and 1% NBS solution in isopropanol) were deposited and annealed at 100 °C for 10 minutes respectively. Once it is cooled down to room temperature, the hole transport layer was deposited. Spiro-OMeTAD (70 mM) was prepared by dissolving the corresponding amount of materials in 1 mL chlorobenzene. Spiro-OMeTAD was doped by adding bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt (Li-TFSI) and 4-*tert*-Butylpyridine (*t*-BP) in the molar ratio 0.5 and 3.3 respectively. 40 μL of HTM solutions were spin-coated atop of the perovskite layer at 4000 rpm for 30 s, in an argon filled glove-box. To finish the device fabrication, silver layer of 100 nm as cathode was thermally evaporated under low vacuum (10⁻⁶ torr). All solutions were prepared inside an argon-filled glove box with controlled moisture and oxygen conditions (O₂ <10 ppm, H₂O < 2 ppm).

Device characterization

The fabricated solar cells figure of merit was measured using current density–voltage (*J–V*) curves, recorded with a Keithley 2400 source-meter under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW cm² illumination from a 450 W AAA solar simulator (ORIEL, 94023 A). NREL certified monocrystalline silicon solar cell was used for calibration. A black metal mask (0.16 cm²) was used over the square size active area (0.5 cm²) to reduce the influence of scattered light.

Photovoltaic parameters including J_{SC} , V_{OC} , fill factor (FF), and power conversion efficiency (PCE) were extracted from the photocurrent–voltage (J – V) curves of the solar cells (scan rate: 100 mV s⁻¹, pre-sweep delay: 10 s). The external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements were carried out using a 150W Xenon lamp attached to with Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4m monochromator as the light source.

Thin film Characterization

The morphology of the surface with and without the passivation layer were examined by the scanning electron microscope (SEM). The thin films were prepared on quartz substrate by spin coating for structural characterization, thin films were prepared by spin coating of pristine $\{(MAPbBr_3)_{0.85}(FAPbI_3)_{0.15}\}$ and (0.3%, 0.5%, 1%) concentration *NBS*/PSK treatment. X-ray diffractograms were recorded using the D8 Advance diffractometer from Bruker (Bragg-Bretanto geometry, with an X-ray tube Cu K α , $\lambda=1.5406$ angstrom). A scan of 5-10° was selected with an acquisition time of 1°/min. The absorption spectra were measured under UV-Vis-IR spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer). Photoluminescence (PL) steady state measurements were recorded with a spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Instrument LS55). X-ray photoluminescence spectroscopy (XPS) were carried out on a SPECS system (BERLIN, GERMANY) equipped with Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analyser with monochromator Al K α radiation (1486.7 eV).

PM-IRRAS spectra of the mixed perovskites spin-coated onto gold substrates (15 × 20 mm), before and after different *NBS* treatment (0.02, 0.2 and 1%), were recorded on a ThermoNicolet Nexus 670 FTIR spectrometer at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ during 4h acquisition time. All spectra were collected in a controlled dry environment (RH = 3%) protected from ambient light. Experiments were performed at an incidence angle of 75° using an external homemade goniometer reflection attachment and adding a ZnSe photoelastic modulator (PEM, Hinds Instruments, type III) after the polarizer. The ATR spectrum of *NBS* compound was recorded

on the same FTIR spectrometer using a Silver-Gate (germanium crystal) ATR accessory (Specac). The ATR spectrum was obtained, at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , by coadding 500 scans. See Table S1 for peak assignment of the vibrational modes of mixed perovskite.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.P. performed the experiments, analyzed the data and prepared the initial draft, S.K. performed the electro-optical measurements and analysis of the data, T.B. and D.M.B. made PMIRRAS measurements and analyzed the data, S.A. supervised and directed the research. All authors contributed to draft and prepared the final version.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Scheme, PM-IRRAS stretching bands, detailed XPS spectra, scanning microscopy images, device statistics, steady state device performance and admittance spectroscopy.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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